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Deliverable D2.5

ARIADNE app for the exploration of MINOTAUR database

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Abstract

This document presents the first release version of the ARIADNE app and web interface. This deliverable is strictly connected with D2.3 (which presented the centralized database development and structure) and has the objective of presenting the application which was developed to visualize, analyse, and explore the data in the database. This document briefly presents development motivation and methods, and finally presents a user guide to the web interface of the application.

Leader: CREA. Participants: BOKU, INRAE

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1 Introduction

Soil host a great biodiversity, including microorganisms (e.g., bacteria), micro- (e.g., Nematoda), meso- (e.g., Collembola), and macrofauna (e.g., Oligochaeta). A great amount of soil biodiversity data have been collected by different European projects or initiatives, such as the LUCAS (Orgiazzi et al., 2016), but much work is still needed to comprehensively harmonize the collected data and metadata. MINOTAUR project in WP2 had the objective of creating appropriate procedures and technological solutions to this aim.

Communicating scientific data is not an easy task, which becomes more daunting with increasing complexity of the data and the context being considered, as in the case of biodiversity in soil. Bridging science and policy is an even greater challenge (McInerney et al. 2014). Scientific data are in fact complex in nature, especially for a non-expert audience, and complex to be translated in policy-relevant language and relevant practical recommendations. Nevertheless this bridge represents a critical aspect and opportunity for decision and policy-making (Roux et al. 2006). Policy makers operate in dynamic environments, where timely decision are crucial, and were priority is on actionable insights and strategic overviews. Their decisions often need to balance urgency, practicality, and public impact; valuing concise summaries, clear visualizations, and the ability to evaluate potential outcomes quickly. As such, overly technical presentations can hinder their comprehension and delay decision-making. Dashboards specifically cater those needs by presenting relevant scientific data in a concise and visually appealing manner. The interactive nature of dashboards permit direct data exploration and visualization, allowing to explore questions in real time to generate a deeper understanding of the challenges at hand. In addition, features like filters, annotations, and straightforward, customizable, visualizations further increasing accessibility. Dashboards specifically designed for policy makers should focus on clarity and usability, presenting high-level insights, key performance indicators, and interactive tools to simulate policy scenarios.

For the above reasons a new task 2.5 was developed within MINOTAUR project through EJPSOIL extension calls. The aim was to create an accessible and informative dashboard to visualize and explore the soil biodiversity data and metadata

that were collected as part of other WP2 actions. This deliverable present the application dashboard that was produced to this aim.

2 Metodological approach

2.1 Motivation

Actions presented in this deliverable directly relates to deliverable D2.1 “Synthesis of soil biodiversity databases”, D2.2 “Distribution of soil biodiversity groups across Europe”, and D2.3 “Data obtained from national LTE registries; including standardization, integration, quality control and pooling with existing data across Europe” of the MINOTAUR project. Collectively, those three deliverables represent the whole MINOTAUR approach for i) identifying suitable data sources among published researches or among suitable datasets from research projects inside the consortium, ii) building a common template for data collection and organizing the data in a centralized database, and iii) collecting European soil biodiversity data in a standardized template, harmonizing data and associated metadata to provide an overview of existing information on different biological groups. The original structure of MINOTAUR project did not directly include any proposed methods and technological solutions to allow for collected data exploration and visualization in a dynamic way. Despite this, a web interface for data query, upload, and download was provided with the OpenADOM system (D2.3 and D2.4).

We can assume that different stakeholders of MINOTAUR project have different needs regard the data that were collected in the database:

- Academic/research stakeholder: we will assume here that this category of stakeholders is either a data producer or a researcher in the field of soil science and biodiversity. This stakeholder has some level of data science proficiency and is likely interested in the data collected by the MINOTAUR consortium, either as a data provider (i.e. uploading data to the MINOTAUR database) or as a data user (i.e. querying and downloading data from the MINOTAUR database for comparison to own data). The infrastructure presented in D2.3, thanks to OpenADOM, provides the methodologies to satisfy the upload, query, and

download requests of this category of stakeholders.

- Policy maker/general public: we assume here that this category of stakeholders receives the greatest benefits from the possibility of interactive exploration of the data collected by the MINOTAUR consortium, with little interest in the actual data, and with maximum interest in understandable visualizations or analysis and remote exploration.

To best answer to the needs of this latter category of stakeholders we developed the “shARed mInotAur Database explorationN Environment” application: **ARIADNE**. Figure 1 briefly depicts the ARIADNE structure

Figure 1 ARIADNE general structure

ARIADNE was entirely developed using Shiny (Chang et al. 2024) in R/Rstudio. Shiny is an R-based framework that simplifies the creation of interactive web tools for data visualization and exploration. One of its major strengths lies in its seamless integration with the R environment, enabling the use of powerful data manipulation, visualization, and statistical modeling typical of R statistical environment, directly within the app. Its flexibility supports the development of fully customizable web user interfaces, while its reactive programming model ensures efficient and dynamic user interactions (i.e. possibility to capture user inputs for query/filter or for personalization of plots). By leveraging Shiny, we were able to focus on delivering insights and functionality without the overhead of extensive and specific coding, making it an ideal choice for our objectives.

At the moment of writing of this document, the following details applies to ARIADNE

Name of the application	ARIADNE
Version	4.0; 27/11/2024
URL	https://ariadne.sk8.inrae.fr/
DB version	November 2024
Documentation	https://github.com/FrancescoVit/ARIADNE/wiki
Code availability/Repository	https://github.com/FrancescoVit/ARIADNE
Code copyright	CC-BY 4.0
DOI	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14244122

2.2 ARIADNE structure: server infrastructure

For the hosting of ARIADNE, the services offered as part of the INRAE's SK8 project (more info for the project available here: https://sk8.pages.mia.inra.fr/projet_sk8) were used. The SK8 project has the objective of offering an R-Shiny Application hosting service, which perfectly matched the needs of MINOTAUR and ARIADNE. More in details, the service offers the possibility to host the code of R-Shiny applications on a GitLab.repository. In addition, the use of an automated workflow allows to generate the containerization of the applications and its implementation in production in a Kubernetes cluster.

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Figure 2 Schematic structure of the hosting service of the SK8 project

3 Results

3.1 User guide to ARIADNE: the user interface

ARIADNE generally focuses on the analysis and display of biodiversity data at different levels, as collected by the MINOTAUR database. Biodiversity data are often complex in structure, multivariate in nature, and, in case of metabarcoding-based analysis, often framed as “big data”. In addition, a successful exploration of biodiversity data greatly benefits from extensive metadata annotation. The feature implement in ARIADNE and the organization of the different sections have been designed keeping those general data aspects in mind, and accounting for the needs of a direct and easily interpretable visualization by our designed stakeholders (i.e. policy maker/general public).

As flexible for interactive exploration, the Shiny framework is also extremely flexible regarding development. For this reason, the ARIADNE application will be continuously evolved over time, gathering feedback from users and colleagues to improve accessibility, appeal of visualization and design of the user interface (GUI), and functionalities. In this deliverable, we will illustrate the GUI and the main analysis or filtering functionalities in ARIADNE v4.0, which might change in the future. For this reason, we have also prepared a user guide in the form of a Wiki in the GitHub repository (available at <https://github.com/FrancescoVit/ARIADNE/wiki>) which reports the content of this deliverable as accompanying guide to the application. A link to the GitHub wiki is also included in the initial page of ARIADNE. In addition, the creation of this repository in GitHub also allows for an easy way to collect user feedback through

the issues system, both on the user interface and on the code part (available at <https://github.com/FrancescoVit/ARIADNE/issues>).

At startup, a welcome/landing page is displayed, reporting a brief description of the application and relevant help link (to the wiki, to the MINOTAUR project page and to the MINOTAUR ZENODO repository to bridge with other products and data from the project).

The application at present is made by two principal sections which are navigable by the menu on the left side: the “Overview” and the “Analysis” sections. Screen-shot from the application with numbers annotation for the different sections that will be explained in the text of this deliverable, will be presented in the following text.

Figure 3 Screenshot of the content of the starting page/overview section of ARIADNE V4.0. Numbers reported in text using [] refers to annotation of the figure

All ARIADNE pages are organized as shown in Figure 3. The application has a black lateral navigation bar on the left [1], which allows for navigation among the different contents of ARIADNE, and a main page area where plots, tables or any other content will be included [2]. At the time of writing of this document, two section are implemented in the navigation bar: the “overview” and the “analysis” section [1]. The

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navigation bar can be collapsed (or expanded) by click on the .

3.2 User guide to ARIADNE: the overview section

The “overview” section (Figure 3) has the aim of allowing for sample filtering on a set of parameter (i.e. land use, management, state, and biota group) [3] and of showing the resulting number of records, respect to total records for which biodiversity data are available [4], as well as a plotting area showing positioning on map of selected records and the count of selected records for each Member State [5]. In addition, sliders can be used to adjust latitude and longitude ranges of map visualization [6]. The filtering menu [3], and any other sections in ARIADNE enclosed in blue boxes can be collapsed and expanded by click on .

Figure 4 reports the content of the filtering menu when expanded. In this menu, further filtering could be implemented in the future application version. In ARIADNE v4.0 we implemented a drop-down filtering on land use, a drop-down filtering on management, a multiple checkbox filtering on biota group to be included or excluded, and a multiple selection box for the Member State to be included (here auto complete of state name is enabled). Information boxes show the results of selected records respect to total records. In Figure 4, for example, we filtered for samples from Italy, France and Germany, for which data on macrofauna are available.

The screenshot shows a 'Sample selection' panel with the following elements:

- Land use:** A dropdown menu currently set to 'All samples'.
- Management:** A dropdown menu currently set to 'All samples'.
- Select biota group to show:** A row of checkboxes for 'Fungi', 'Microfauna', 'Mesofauna', and 'Macrofauna'. The 'Macrofauna' checkbox is checked.
- Select State:** A text input field containing the letters 'IT', 'FR', and 'DE'.

Below the selection panel are two summary cards:

- TOTAL SELECTED RECORDS:** 1890
- BIOTA GROUP SELECTED RECORDS:** 1263

Figure 4 Example of filtering menu in ARIADNE V4.0

The “Overview” section has the objective of generally allowing for filtering/selection of desired records, and for an evaluation of their geographical positioning. Moreover, the “Overview” section also has the objective of setting the subset of samples on which to

perform further analysis collected in the “Analysis” section. All analysis and visualization included in the different sections of “Analysis” section, in fact, will be performed on the records subset that is selected by filters in the “Overview” section.

3.3 User guide to ARIADNE: the analysis section

The “Analysis” section (Figure 5) has the aim of displaying a selected set of statistical analysis and visualizations, for the subset of records that were selected in the “Overview” section. The “Analysis” section is organized in sub-section, or tabs, depending on the type of data analyzed.

Figure 5 Screenshot of the content of the analysis section of ARIADNE V4.0. Numbers reported in text using [] refers to annotation of the figure

The first level of content organization is based on the type of data that is considered. The first level of organization divides the data by its typology [1]. The GUI represents this division by using different selectable tabs with the name of the data type considered. We have divided the different biodiversity measures we collected in three families:

- A) *Quantitative indices*: that assess the abundance (number of individuals) or biomass (weight or mass of organisms) of specific taxa within an ecosystem.
- B) *Biodiversity indices*: that measure the diversity of species within a given area or

ecosystem. These indices account for both the number of species (species richness), their relative abundance or distribution (species evenness) or a combination of this aspects (eg. shannon index)

C) *Ecological indices*: that focus on the functional roles and contributions of taxa within ecosystems. Rather than simply assessing abundance or diversity, these indices aim to understand how species interact with each other and their environment, and how they contribute to ecological processes such as nutrient cycling, soil structure etc.

The second level of organization is based on the biota level considered for analysis [2]. For each measurement tab, in fact, different collapsed blue boxes will be displayed, each of which reports data of a specific level of soil biota.

Upon expansion of collapsed blue boxes, actual analysis will be displayed with a series of tailored statistics and graphics. An example is reported in Figure 6 for the Mesofauna biota level. In this case, the results about the QBS-ar index (ecological measurements tab) are reported in the form of a boxplot [1] and table [2], the latter reporting numerical value of the data distribution: different percentiles (10th, 12.5th, 25th, 50th, 75th, 87.5th, and 90th), minimum value, maximum value, average, and number of records.

Figure 6 Screenshot of the content of the analysis section of ARIADNE V4.0 for mesofauna in the ecological measurements tab for cases of categorical explanatory variable. Numbers reported in text using [] refers to annotation of the figure

The data can be explored based on different explanatory variables (i.e. metadata), which can be selected by a dropdown menu [3]. The different levels of explanatory variable for selected measure are used in visualization and statistic for comparison. In Figure 6, for example, the “Land use” explanatory variable is used, which is composed

by three levels: “arable land”, “grass land” and “permanent crop”. Consequently, those same categories are reported in boxplot visualization [1] and in numerical table report [2]. Moreover, a Kruskal Wallis test for overall statistical differences of selected measure based on explanatory variable is performed [4] and a pairwise test between different levels of the explanatory variable is visualized in [5] (reporting only the significant comparisons)

Figure 7 Screenshot of the content of the analysis section of ARIADNE V4.0 for mesofauna in the ecological measurements tab for cases of numerical explanatory variable. Numbers reported in text using [] refers to annotation of the figure

If a numerical explanatory variable is selected [1], the kind of output displayed changes, and a scatterplot like visualization is reported [2] (Figure 7). In those cases, the user can optionally visualize a line on the plot for a specific threshold value, for scenario exploration. Moreover, the table reported in [3] will only have one level generically reporting the numerical value of variable distribution, and results of Pearson and Spearman correlation will be reported in [4]

4 Discussion and conclusions

With ARIADNE we provide an environment for exploration and visualization of the data collected as part of MINOTAUR project. ARIADNE is designed to assist non-technical/scientific users, for example policy makers, in the exploration of soil biodiversity data, using a responsive web-based solution, tailored to their specific

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needs. In addition, ARIADNE is developed with methods allowing for a high customizability of both the user interface and the statistical/data elaboration happening backend. We will aim at collecting user feedback upon release of the deliverable, and upon circulation in the EJP-Soil network, from target users as policy makers for continuous improvement. No major maintenance expenses are needed for the app as it is hosted on server internal to the INRAE partner of the project and will be maintained as long as the MINOTAUR database. The app will always be up to date with the MINOTAUR database via csv files export, which are its starting data source. In addition, being based on csv import as starting data source, instead of direct SQL interaction with the database, the ARIADNE could easily ingest data from other large initiatives like Eudaphobase or EUSO, provided that data are included using standard MINOTAUR templates. Interaction with these initiatives, in any case, in the future can also be performed leveraging SQL language, which is supported by the Shiny framework

5 List of references

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